

Bringing Digital Humanities to the wider public: libraries as incubator for DH research results

Martijn Kleppe*

* National Library of the Netherlands

Abstract

Digital Humanities researchers rely on large digital datasets. Since the National Library of the Netherlands (KB) has been digitizing its collection for about ten years, their datasets are popular amongst DH scholars that focus on historical newspapers, periodicals and books. By not only supporting researchers by giving them access to datasets, but also by collaborating with them, the KB aims to incorporate DH research results in their services and products. We do this by sharing our prototype tools and code on our online Lab, invite academics to come and work as researcher-in-residence and are full partner in research projects. In this talk I will describe the challenges and opportunities for libraries and academics when they collaborate. What can researchers gain from collaborating with libraries? And how can libraries bring the affordances of DH research to the wider public?

Bio

Martijn Kleppe is Head of the Research Department of the National Library of the Netherlands (KB). Trained as historian, he wrote a dissertation on photographic iconic images by building and applying computational techniques. Before moving to the KB, he was a researcher in several Digital Humanities that focused on opening up audiovisual and textual archives by using techniques from the National Language Processing Domain, speech recognition and computer vision. At the KB, he now leads the Research Department that covers topics such as digital preservation, copyright, public library research, digital scholarship and improving the usability and discoverability of digital content.